

FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IS A PATH TO IMPROVED HEALTH

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Abstract. *A healthy lifestyle helps us fulfill our goals and objectives, successfully implement our plans, cope with difficulties, and, if necessary, with colossal overloads. Good health, maintained and strengthened by the person himself, will allow him to live a long and joyful life. The main component of a person's lifestyle is his work, which represents the purposeful activity of a person aimed at creating material and spiritual values. A person's lifestyle must be subordinated, first of all, to his effective work activity. A working person lives in a certain rhythm: he must get up at a certain time, perform his duties, eat, rest and sleep.*

Keywords: *formation, healthy, lifestyle, path, improved, component, health.*

Relevance. A healthy lifestyle is an individual system of human behavior that provides him with physical, mental and social well-being in the real environment (natural, man-made and social) and active longevity. A healthy lifestyle creates the best conditions for the normal course of physiological and mental processes, which reduces the likelihood of various diseases and increases human life expectancy. Good health, maintained and strengthened by the person himself, will allow him to live a long and joyful life. [5] The main component of a person's lifestyle is his work, which represents the purposeful activity of a person aimed at creating material and spiritual values. A person's lifestyle must be subordinated, first of all, to his effective work activity. A working person lives in a certain rhythm: he must get up at a certain time, perform his duties, eat, rest and sleep. And this is not surprising - all processes in nature are subject to a strict rhythm to one degree or another: the seasons alternate, night follows day, day again comes to replace night. Rhythmic activity is one of the basic laws of life and one of the foundations of any work. A rational combination of elements of a lifestyle ensures more productive human work and a high level of health. The whole organism as a whole participates in human labor activity. The work rhythm sets the physiological rhythm: at certain hours the body experiences stress, as a result of which metabolism increases, blood circulation increases, and then a feeling of fatigue appears; at other hours and days, when the load is reduced, rest comes after fatigue, strength and energy are restored. Proper alternation of load and rest is the basis for high human performance. Now we need to dwell on the issue of rest. [2] Rest is a state of rest or active activity leading to restoration of strength and performance. The most effective way to restore performance is active rest, which allows you to rationally use your free time. Alternating types of work, a harmonious combination of mental and physical labor, and physical education ensure effective restoration of strength and energy. A person needs to rest daily, weekly on weekends, annually during the next vacation, using free time to strengthen physical and spiritual health. A healthy lifestyle is a set of forms and methods of everyday cultural activity of an individual, based on cultural norms, values, meanings of activity and strengthening the adaptive capabilities of the body and ensuring harmonious development, maintaining and strengthening health, high performance, and also allows you to reveal the most valuable qualities of the individual, necessary in the conditions of the dynamic development of our society[1]. Preserving the health of the younger generation is one of the most important social

tasks of society; in order to prepare highly qualified specialists, it is necessary to strengthen and form a healthy lifestyle and promote the working capacity of young people. Today, this category of the population is experiencing the negative impact of the environment, since physical and mental development coincides with the period of adaptation to new, changed living conditions, learning, and high mental stress. Adolescence may be critical to future health and illness because there is some evidence that habits learned during this period can be followed into adulthood. For example, alcohol habits during adolescence increase the likelihood of heavy consumption in adulthood, and food consumption during adolescence is an indicator of consumption in adulthood. For this reason, some chronic diseases may have their origin and disease progression in adolescence. To improve adolescent health, it is important to promote healthy behaviors at an early age, especially during adolescence. The main health behaviors associated with adolescents are physical activity, less time on multimedia, healthy eating and avoidance of alcohol and tobacco use, as well as caffeine/stimulant use, sleep deprivation, drug use, condomless sex and unhealthy relationships [5]. The results from the literature, conducted in different countries, indicate that currently the following are essential for modern student youth: money, education and profession, business career and pleasure. For the majority of modern youth, the desire for well-being, which is based on enrichment and success in life, achieved at any cost, sometimes at the expense of their individual health and the health of the people around them. [2] At the same time, the forms, methods, and teaching aids implemented in practice today do not allow us to fully ensure the implementation of a person-oriented approach to the formation of a healthy lifestyle for young people and do not meet the requirements for the training of a modern specialist. The reason for this situation is, on the one hand, insufficient promotion of a healthy lifestyle. Research on adolescent health habits has focused on the relationship between individual behavior and its health outcomes. Average values of healthy behavior decreased significantly in all countries from age 11 to age 15. Adilson Marques highlighted the fact that much work still needs to be done to promote healthy lifestyles and increase adolescents' awareness of the potential benefits to their health status. Given that it is known that health behaviors are established during this period of development, understanding how best to promote healthy lifestyles is critical during this stage of life. Research on adolescent health habits has focused on the relationship between individual behavior and its health outcomes. Average values of healthy behavior decreased significantly in all countries from age 11 to age 15. Adilson Marques highlight the fact that much work still needs to be done to promote healthy lifestyles and increase adolescents' awareness of the potential benefits to their health status. Given that it is known that health behaviors are established during this period of development, understanding how best to promote healthy lifestyles is critical during this stage of life. [3] The problem of developing a healthy lifestyle for young people is multifaceted. The younger generation studying in colleges, institutes and universities are supporters of a certain lifestyle, in which cigarettes, alcohol and drugs are the ideal. The results of the research conducted by the author Kobenko D.V. shows that the factors influencing the formation of a healthy lifestyle for young people are factors that improve health and worsen health Factors that improve health include: absence of bad habits, balanced nutrition, physical education and sports, morning exercises, study and rest regime, hardening of the body, the following positive emotions, absence of harmful factors in educational activities, walks in the fresh air, favorable climatic conditions life, a high level of preventive measures, timely and comprehensive medical care. Factors that improve health include: absence of bad habits, balanced nutrition, physical education and sports,

morning exercises, study and rest regime, hardening of the body, the following positive emotions, absence of harmful factors in educational activities, walks in the fresh air, favorable climatic conditions life, a high level of preventive measures, timely and comprehensive medical care. Factors that worsen health include: improperly organized daily routine, bad habits, stressful situations, intensification of the educational process, mental overload, unbalanced nutrition, physical inactivity, unsatisfactory sanitary and hygienic conditions of classrooms, poor material resources, lack of constant medical supervision. [4] To form a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to find out what causes an unhealthy lifestyle and what contributes to maintaining a healthy lifestyle. To determine the cause, preventive work is being carried out in many places to promote a healthy lifestyle, as well as to identify the physical, social and psychological health of young people. A diagnostic analysis of the state of their physical, social and mental health confirms that all students have different lifestyles, different health, and different goals. To create a healthy lifestyle, you must follow the following daily routine:

- it is advisable to get up at the same time every day;
- try to regularly do morning exercises;
- eat at set hours;
- alternate mental and physical work;
- observe the rules of personal hygiene;
- work and sleep in a well-ventilated area, go to bed at the same time.

The formation of a healthy lifestyle in the educational process is the most important task of society. In this regard, it is necessary to encourage young people to preserve and improve health, to promote and support a culture of a healthy lifestyle. It is necessary to introduce into the educational process knowledge aimed at developing a healthy lifestyle, starting from a very early age, and engage in self-education of the individual. Thus, organized propaganda of medical and hygienic knowledge helps reduce the level of diseases and helps raise a strong generation. The formation of a healthy lifestyle in the educational process is the most important task of society. In this regard, it is necessary to encourage young people to preserve and improve health, to promote and support a culture of a healthy lifestyle. It is necessary to introduce into the educational process knowledge aimed at developing a healthy lifestyle, starting from a very early age, and engage in self-education of the individual. Thus, organized propaganda of medical and hygienic knowledge helps reduce the level of diseases and helps raise a strong generation. In the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the most important role should be the role of educational programs aimed at preserving and strengthening the health of young people, the formation of active motivation to care for their health and the health of those around them. Protecting our own health is the obligation of each of us, and this obligation should not be transferred to others. After all, it happens that by the age of 30 a person brings himself to a hopeless state through an incorrect lifestyle. And therefore, from an early age it is necessary to take care of your health, because “the disease will not catch up with the quick and agile” [5]

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